

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

MODIFIED WITH EPICHLOROHYDRIN COMPOSITE BASED ON BENZOGUANAMINE-FORMALDEHYDE OLIGOMER

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Abstract

Composites made on the basis of oligomers are used in industry and everyday life for various purposes, and demand is growing day by day. The reason is that it is easy to process and economical. However, composites made on the basis of existing oligomers have certain disadvantages during operation. To eliminate these shortcomings, the method of copolycondensation with epichlorohydrin benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer used as the object of the study was modified. The modification process was carried out in two stages. At the first stage of formaldehyde with benzoguanamine 1:2 mol. proportionally, in a slightly alkaline medium, at 70-75^oC, the condensation process was carried out for 60-70 minutes until a homogeneous solution was obtained in a laboratory reactor. At the second stage, the calculated amount of epichlorohydrin is gradually added and continuously mixed until a solid juice of a similar mass is obtained. The resulting polymer is a light-yellow compound, highly soluble in acetone, ethanol, dioxane, tetrahydrofuran and dimethylformamide. In parallel, the main physicochemical, physico-mechanical, operational parameters and spectral analysis of the benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer and the epichlorohydrin-modified benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer were studied for the purpose of comparison. It turned out that after the modification process, fragility was eliminated, adhesion ability increased, and most importantly, the number of free monomers decreased. From the analysis of the analysis results, it became clear that the process is a chemical modification, and the disadvantage is the presence of functional epoxy groups in epichlorohydrines. The curing process of the modified epichlorohydrin cooligomer is carried out thermally at different temperatures and at different times. The optimal solidification rate of the cooligomer was 98.86 % at 140 ^oC for 5 hours.

Taking into account the functional groups present in the oligomer, the composition of the coating was developed using it as a binder. Organic and inorganic fillers, hardeners and acetone as a solvent were used in the manufacture of the composite. The prepared coating composition is recommended to be used for corrosion protection of equipment operated in various environments.

Keywords: benzoguanamin, formaldehyd, epichlorhidrin

Composites are compact materials obtained by mixing various components. The structure of composites is complex, and the reason is that it depends on the components that make it up. The basic physical, mechanical and technological indicators of composites are higher than the indicators of its individual components.

The main purpose of the research work is to obtain, first of all, a reactive cooligomer and to obtain composites based on it. To obtain a reactive oligomer, the existing benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer was modified into epichlorohydrin, its functionality was further enhanced, and as a result, a new composition cooligomer was obtained. The basic physico-chemical, physico-mechanical, operational and spectral analyses of the oligomer obtained as a result of copolycondensation of components with chemical modification have been studied.

For the purpose of comparison, an unmodified benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer was studied in parallel. A new composition of the paint coating was developed, in which an oligomer was used as a binder, and the main technological indicators were studied. The

durability of the paintwork composition in various environments has been studied.

It is known that a radical improvement in the environmental situation can be achieved by improving both the physical and mechanical and operational performance of composites used in various industries, as well as the development of environmentally friendly technologies [1-4].

Currently, research works aimed at the complete absence of the number of free monomers in their composition are of relevance. The solution to this problem has both economic and environmental significance. Thus, an important role is played by the use of modern system analysis methods that allow to identify the mechanism and the main kinetic patterns of reactions, to determine the optimal conditions for obtaining an environmentally friendly product.

The polycondensation reaction of the benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer with epichlorohydrin leads to the production of an amino-epoxide-containing oligomer when the pH of the medium = 7-8. As a result, the number of free

monomers decreases, and the functionality of the cooligomer increases.

When changing the ratios between the components, it is possible to adjust the main homogeneity indicators obtained in the direction corresponding to the purpose. In the process, the amount of free formaldehyde decreased by about 2.5 times.

Due to the functional groups, the adhesive ability and heat resistance are also increased. It is advisable to obtain composites for various purposes using a new cooligomer composition as a binder, obtained as a result of identifying the main patterns of copolycondensation in an alkaline medium and determining optimal heat exchange conditions.

Aggressive media include coating compositions used in the oil and gas industry to protect operated equipment and installations from corrosion, to reservoir waters, to oils-to gasoline, etc. its durability is explained by the high functionality of the binder, and it is recommended to use benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer modified with epichlorohydrin, as a binder in the preparation of the paint composition.

Eksperimental part

The process of modification of the benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer with epichlorohydrin by copolycondensation was carried out in a laboratory reactor equipped with a stirrer, a thermometer and an anti-cooler. First, benzoguanamine is injected into the laboratory reactor: formaldehyde (37% formaldehyde solution in water-formalin) in a ratio of 1: 2 mol and up to 2% NaOH of the reaction mass. The blender is started and at 70-75 °C the reaction

medium is continuously stirred for 1.0-1.5 hours at pH = 7.0-8.0. Then 0.5 mol of epichlorohydrin is gradually added to the reactor and continuously stirred until a juice-like mass is obtained (~ 1.0-1.5 hours). The resulting oligomer is dried in a vacuum drying cabinet to a constant mass.

The main physico-chemical and physico-mechanical parameters of the benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer modified with epichlorohydrin have been studied [5-7]. The influence of the number of components on the output of the oligomer has been studied.

With the ratio of benzoguanamine : formaldehyde : epichlorohydrin = 1 : 2 : 0.5 mol, the oligomer yield was 70%. Cooligomer is highly soluble in acetone, dioxane, tetrahydrofuran, dimethylformamide and alcohol. Does not dissolve in water, gasoline, CCl₄ and benzene.

The main indicators of the cooligomer are shown in Table 1. It turned out that the corresponding indicators of the cooligomer are higher compared to the main indicators of the benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer.

To determine the effective use of the synthesized new cooligomer, thermal degradation in the temperature range 100 ÷ 500 °C was studied on the G-1500 DMOM derivator. The mass of the sample is 0.2 g., TG is the sensitivity of the scale 200, the sensitivity of the galvanometer DTA = DTG = 50 μV, the rate of temperature increase in the derivatograph is 5°/ min., the speed of movement of the automatic writing drum is 2.5 mm/min., the tests were carried out in PT/PtRh putas under atmospheric conditions. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 1

The main indicators of the oligomer and cooligomer

№	Indicators	Oligomer	Cooligomer
1.	The composition of the element, %		
	Carbon	63.82	65.36
	Hydrogen	4.38	4.74
	Nitrogen	3.59	3.84
	Chlorine	-	6.7
2.	Softening temperature, °C	65	70
3.	Mass of molecules	470	685
4.	Density, kg/m ³	1050	1120
5.	Degree of curing, % (within 5 hours at 140 °C)	96.8	98.86
6.	Adhesive strength, MPa	2.1	2.8

Table 2

Indicators of thermal degradation of the oligomer and cooligomer

№	Examples	Indicators			
		T _{5%} , °C	T _{1/2} , °C	E _{dis.} , kkal/mol	E _a , kkal/mol
1.	Benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer	106	298	56.4	3.1
2.	Benzoquanamine-formaldehyde cooligomer modified with epichlorohydrin	110	483	67.1	3.3

The Molecular Mass Distribution (MMD) of the modified epichlorohydrin benzoguanamine-formaldehyde oligomer was studied by liquid chromatography on a Rovo chromatograph (Czech Republic). The MMD indicators of compounds

obtained both by polycondensation and by copolycondensation are shown in Table 3.

It turned out that the molecular distribution of the oligomer is 1.33, and the molecular distribution of the cooligomer is 2.09, that is, the fraction with a higher molecular weight is precisely the cooligomer.

Table 3

Molecular weight distribution

№	Examples	MMD		
		$\overline{M}_w$	$\overline{M}_n$	$\overline{M}_w/\overline{M}_n$
1.	Oligomer	360	270	1.33
2.	Cooligomer	900	430	2.09

From the analysis of IR spectra, it also became known that the process is a chemical modification, and due to the functional groups present in the components (amine, carbonyl and epoxy), the cooligomer was obtained.

From the comparative analysis of the cooligomer of benzoguanamine-formaldehyde, modified for the first time by epichlorohydrin, with the unmodified oligomer of benzoguanamine-formaldehyde, it is known that many factors influence the reduction of free monomers in the cooligomer, the increase in the basic physico-chemical and physico-mechanical parameters (the ratio of components, their structure, nature, temperature, reaction time, etc.) affects. The pH of the reaction medium is 7-8, the temperature is 70-75 °C, the amount of the modifier is 0.5 mol.

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